

Tracing cosmic magnetic fields using molecules

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The Universe is permeated by magnetic fields, that often play an important role in the dynamics of astrophysical processes [1]. Observations of spiral galaxies generally reveal magnetic field strengths on the order of $\sim 10 \mu\text{G}$ [2], while molecular clouds in star-forming regions are associated with dynamically important magnetic fields [1]. All main-sequence stars are thought to host a magnetic field, which is likely boosted through a stellar dynamo [3], and inherited as the star evolves away from the main-sequence as an evolved star [4]. The magnetic field in all these phases will affect the dynamics of the associated astrophysical processes. To characterize the effects, one requires information on both the magnetic field strength, and morphology.

With the advent of (sub)millimeter interferometers, it has been possible to analyze the (polarized) emission of astrophysical sources at sub-arcsecond resolution. This has opened up the possibility of studying the resolved structure of many astrophysical sources. Molecular line polarization traces magnetic fields at these scales most robustly. Here, we discuss different techniques of magnetic field detection with molecules. We discuss mapping of magnetic field morphology with (sub-)millimeter interferometry techniques using (i) the Goldreich-Kylafis effect [5] and collisional polarization [6], to map the magnetic field morphology and (ii) through the Zeeman effect of paramagnetic molecules, tracing the magnetic field strength. We also discuss using masers (Microwave Amplification of Stimulated Emission of Radiation) to trace the magnetic field strength and morphology towards high-mass star-forming regions.

Line polarization: PORTAL & collisional polarization

Linear polarization in molecular lines is found in non-LTE excited molecular species, that are under the influence of an anisotropic radiation field [7]. Because the magnetic precession rate of non-paramagnetic molecules is on the order of $\sim s^{-1}/\text{mG}$, while other aligning interactions typically occur at rates of $\lesssim 10^{-4} s^{-1}$, molecules almost always orient themselves to the magnetic field under astrophysical conditions and their polarization direction is related to the magnetic field direction. Molecules therefore provide for a very robust magnetic field tracer.

However, to properly model the polarization of molecular lines, comprehensive radiative transfer modeling, that takes into account the intricate density, velocity and temperature structures of astrophysical sources, is vital. Line radiative transfer modeling tools, such as LIME (Line Modeling Engine, [8]) have been developed to perform such comprehensive modeling for three-dimensional astrophysical structures. In [7], it was shown how to extend a three-dimensional line radiative transfer with the capability to model line polarization radiative transfer, for arbitrary magnetic field configurations.

The polarized line radiative transfer modeling tool is called PORTAL (POLarized Radiative Transfer Adapted to Lines). The source code of PORTAL is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/blankhaar/PORTAL>. PORTAL allows for the rigorous prediction and modeling of line polarization signals from arbitrary astrophysical regions with arbitrary magnetic field configurations.

Figure 1: Plots of the azimuthally averaged polarized emission of transitions of HCN and CO from a face-on axisymmetric disk of mass $10 M_J$. We plot the $J = 3 \rightarrow 2$ and $J = 2 \rightarrow 1$ transitions of CO and the $J = 4 \rightarrow 3$ and $J = 3 \rightarrow 2$ transitions of HCN at systemic velocity. We assume a source of distance 60 pc and a beam size (FWHM) of $0.7'' \times 0.7''$. The polarized emission is computed for a toroidal magnetic field configuration. We also plot the total emission divided by 1000 associated with each transition in a dotted line of the same color to represent the (current) ALMA sensitivity limit of the detectability of linear polarization. We also added a dotted line, representing $1\times$ and $3\times$ a typical ALMA sensitivity of 1.3 mJy/beam. Taken from [9].

Lines may also polarize through collisional polarization if two collision partners interact through oriented collisions [10]. Recently, we pointed out [6] that oriented collisions in astrophysical settings may be the product of ambipolar diffusion. Ambipolar diffusion is generally thought to be one of the most important regulators of star formation, and it occurs in a magnetized and partially ionized plasma, where the neutral and ionized medium are collisionally coupled [11]. In star-forming regions or clouds, a molecular ion such as HCO^+ has as its main collision partner the neutral H_2 . Collisions between these molecules have a preferred direction when ambipolar diffusion is active. In [6], we modeled the collision-induced alignment of HCO^+ and the associated polarization of its spectral lines, under the influence of ambipolar diffusion. It is predicted that detectable polarization emerges in the C-shock associated with the accretion onto young stellar objects [12] or generally in the colder phase of the ISM.

Detecting collisional polarization would be the first direct observation of ambipolar diffusion.

Line polarization opportunities

The formation of solar type stars is accompanied by a protoplanetary disk. Magnetic fields are fundamental to the accretion dynamics of protoplanetary disks and they likely affect planet formation. Zeeman measurements of paramagnetic molecules have been able to put stringent constraints on the magnetic field of protoplanetary disks [13, 14], but have yet to make a direct detection of the global magnetic field in these objects. In Figure 1, we show PORTAL modeling of the polarization signal from the ALMA band 6 and 7 CO and HCN transitions that are excited in a protoplanetary disk such as the one around TW Hya. PORTAL modeling predicts detectable polarization signals for the band 7 transition of HCN, that trace the magnetic field structure around 60 au from the central protostar. Polarization signals of CO are estimated to be weak, which is in line with earlier ALMA line polarization observations [15].

The loss of mass in evolved stars forms a circumstellar envelope around these objects. Molecules form in the envelope and the dust that is produced in the extended atmosphere, absorbs the radiation from the central stellar objects, driving an outward wind. Magnetic fields possibly play an important role in the wind-launching, but are very hard to characterize in these objects. Line polarization in these regions are expected to be strong, due to the strong directional radiative interactions of the stellar radiation field with molecular vibrational transitions [7]. Special care has to be taken here to characterize the aligning interactions (magnetic vs. radiative), but comprehensive and resolved high-resolution line observations may provide important constraints on the magnetic field morphology of these objects.

Some galaxies, such as NGC 4418, host a CON (Compact Obscured Nucleus). CONs are characteristic of a highly dynamical evolutionary stage, associated with a large inflow and a collimated outflow of gas. In turn, the CON is uniquely characterized by very bright vibrationally excited emission, in particular the vibrational transitions of HCN (HCN-VIB). HCN-VIB is pumped by hot ($T > 100K$) dust in the inner ($r < 15 - 75$ pc) and opaque

($N_{\text{H}_2} \geq 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) regions centered on the nuclei. PORTAL simulations show that the vibrationally excited transitions are prone to polarize to very high degrees, because of the strong radiative vibrational excitation in the war inner regions of the CON. The predicted polarization degrees are observable with ALMA. Such observations would constitute the first direct constraints on the magneto-hydrodynamic (MHD) dynamics of the outflow-launching region of a CON.

The simplest example of an anisotropic radiation is field is the astrophysical maser, which is (almost) one-dimensional due to maser beaming [16]. They are therefore also prototypical examples of radiative transfer systems wherein polarized emission arises. Masers occur under special conditions towards many interesting astrophysical objects. We highlight here methanol masers; which occur exclusively towards high-mass star forming regions. Recent theoretical efforts were able to characterize the Zeeman effect in methanol [17], which now opens up the possibility of using this maser as a probe for the magnetic field strength towards massive protostars. Recent developments in the theory of the polarized radiative transfer of masers will allow for the proper interpretation of coming maser polarization observations [18, 19].

References

- [1] Crutcher, R.M. 2012, *Ann.Rev. A&A*, 50, 29-63
- [2] Beck, R. 2016, *A&A Rev.*, 24, 4
- [3] Parker, E.N. 1955, *ApJ*, 122, 293
- [4] Vlemmings, W.H.T. 2019, *Proc. IAU*, 343, 14
- [5] Goldreich, P., & Kylafis, N. 1981, *ApJL*, 243, L75
- [6] Lankhaar, B., & Vlemmings, W. 2020, *A&A*, 638, L7
- [7] Lankhaar, B., & Vlemmings, W. 2020, *A&A*, 636, A14
- [8] Brinch, C., & Hogherheijde, M. 2010, *A&A*, 523, A25
- [9] Lankhaar, B., & Vlemmings, W. 2021, *A&A*, *subm.*
- [10] Fiedrich, B., & Herschbach, D.R. 1991, *Nature*, 353, 412
- [11] Mestel, L., & Spitzer, L. 1956, *MNRAS*, 116, 503
- [12] Li, Z., et al. 2011, *ApJ*, 738, 180
- [13] Vlemmings, W. H. T., et al. 2019, *A&A*, 624, L7
- [14] Harrison, R.E., et al. 2021, *ApJ*, 908, 141
- [15] Stephens, Ian W, et al. 2020, *ApJ*, 901, 71
- [16] Elitzur, M. 1992, *Ann.Rev. A&A*, 30, 75
- [17] Lankhaar, B., et al. 2018, *Nature Astronomy*, 2, 145
- [18] Lankhaar, B., & Vlemmings, W. 2019, *A&A*, 628, A14
- [19] Dall'Olio, D., et al. 2020, *A&A*, 644, A122

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